

STEAM - THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN BASED ON EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

Abdumajitova Sayohat Abdukasimovna

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of the Department of Preschool Education Methodology

Annotation: *Today, the use of STEAM educational technology, a new teaching method of organizing children's activities in a mixed method, is important in the education of preschool children. The variability of education and training is the basic principle and principle of the development of the modern preschool education system in our country today . This STEAM is a variable part of the program , which ensures the quality of the educational process and creates optimal conditions for their social and personal development, taking into account the physical and mental health of preschool children, the trajectory of individual creative development, provided pedagogical skills for studying at school and adapting to the surrounding community ¹in order to implement psychological and physical development .*

Key words: *STEAM, program, education, preschool age, technology, interest, engineering, robotics, visual activity, creativity, intellectual, game, research.*

STEAM is one of the modern educational methods , which envisages a blended learning environment and shows the preschool child how to use science and art in everyday life.

Aunan "STEAM - technology" allows society to breed a generation of ambitious and successful researchers, inventors, scientists, technologists, artists and mathematicians. It is based on the implementation of interdisciplinary and practical cooperation, as well as on the integration of all five areas into a single development

¹ <http://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=12858062>

scheme. At first glance, STEAM is considered a complex concept, but it is actually encoded in a very simple way:²

- S – science (natural sciences),
- T - technology (technology, construction),
- E - engineering (technical creativity),
- A – art (fine arts),
- M - match- mathematics (first mathematical concepts) .

Figure 1. STEAM technology acronym content.

Educators, pedagogues, students and their parents (legal representatives) of preschool educational organization can use STEAM technology based on educational needs.

STEAM technology is a modular field of education , the purpose of which is to develop the possibility of engaging the child's intellectual abilities in scientific and technical creativity ³. Each module is aimed at solving specific problems with a complex solution, such as STEAM education:

- to serve to ensure the realization of a person's goals;
- to develop intellectual abilities in the process of learning and involve them in order to increase the scientific and technical creativity of preschool children .

² <https://infourok.ru/>

³ <http://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=25127015>

STEAM educational technology includes the educational activity process of the preschool educational organization and the development of preschool children's interest in science, technology, education, culture, and the creation of an environment that ensures the formation of their creative thinking and initiative abilities . .

" STEAM technology":

- Develop interest
- of engineering skills
- Enables acquisition of qualities necessary for work (team)
- to analyze the results of the work performed
- to optimal cognitive performance .

As a result of the implementation of innovative STEAM technology in the educational process, it is possible to create a high-level, changing educational process for the development of technological concepts in the fields of robotics, mathematics, natural sciences, engineering graphics, scientific research and research of preschool children. will be _ Based on the positive experiences of developing countries in the implementation of STEAM technology in the educational process with preschool children, it is possible to organize the elements of this technology in the activities of young children .

The purpose of implementing this technology in preschool education is to create a stimulating educational environment model based on STEAM technologies to develop children's intellectual abilities in the process of cognitive activity and involve them in scientific and technical creativity at all stages of preschool childhood .

With the educational reform, STEAM technology was introduced in the presidential schools of Uzbekistan. Introduction of STEAM teaching technology to preschool education organizations , which is the first link of the educational system in the country , accelerates and facilitates the early development of children who are

interested in learning and seeking new knowledge in preschool. But if a child struggles to learn in his program, we need to be patient without forcing him , and instead of waiting for them to learn, we need to allow them to learn . We can use it as a toy to develop a child 's creativity and engineering thinking . We can make some of the types of STEAM games for children with our own hands.

Table 1.

Implementation of STEAM technology in a preschool educational organization is necessary - conditions ⁴have been developed and they are:

Important conditions for the implementation of STEAM technology in a preschool educational organization:	
1	Analysis of existing models of a stimulating educational environment for the development of the necessary conditions for the scientific and technical creativity and intellectual activity of children at all stages of preschool age .
2	Development of the material and technical base of the preschool education organization, development of the program and method of support of the use of STEAM technologies in working with preschool children
3	Adaptation of preschool children to the modern educational environment, integration of various activity content of preschool children in it, intersection of learning tools and materials in space , availability of equipment for independent activity, possibility to show results
4	Skills in the process of scientific and technical creativity .
5	Ensure the formation and motivation ⁵ of the competences of pedagogical staff in working with preschool children using STEAM technologies.

⁴ <http://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=27633158>

⁵ <http://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=12858062>

Initially, this fraternity was simply called STEM without the creative component. But art is very important for all-round development, so it was decided to add the letter A to the term (ART- Art) .

With the educational reform, STEAM technology was introduced in the presidential schools of Uzbekistan. Introduction of STEAM teaching technology to preschool education organizations , which is the first link of the educational system in the country , accelerates and facilitates the early development of children who are interested in learning and seeking new knowledge in preschool. But if a child struggles to learn in his program, we need to be patient without forcing him , and instead of waiting for them to learn, we need to allow them to learn . We can use it as a toy to develop a child 's creativity and engineering thinking. We can make some of the types of STEAM games for children with our own hands.

GVShakina 's article " Problema gotovnosti uchitelya nachalnyx klassov k deyatelnosti po formirovaniyu obshcheuchebnyx umeniy mladshix shkolnikov " published in 2009 spoke about creating a developmental environment through STEAM technology :

"STEAM learning technology is an educational technology that creates a stimulating environment of preschool education aimed at developing intellectual abilities in the process of cognitive activity and attracting scientific and technical creativity :

- affects the intellectual development of preschool children;
- allows the teacher to combine education, training and development of preschool children in the home mode;
- forms cognitive activity, promotes the education of a socially active person, forms communication and co-creation skills ;
- combines o ' uin with research and experimental activity;
- children learn to count, measure , and compare in the learning method;
- encourages the acquisition of necessary mathematical and engineering skills."

The STEAM course focuses on practical application, but changes the order of the core subjects . This includes incorporating STEM disciplines such as engineering, natural sciences, and the humanities and creative arts to form a technology curriculum : literature, design, architecture, music, visual arts, and more. STEM sciences and technology provide concrete solutions to practical problems, while the humanities develop the ability to find a way out of uncertainty. Thus, students learn to combine science , rigor and creative freedom in their work .

References:

1. S. Abdumajidova. STEAM teaching technology in preschool educational organizations . Modern trends of psychological services in the educational system; theory and practice. Republican Scientific and Practical Conference 2022
2. S. Abdumajidova. Organization of development centers in preschool educational organizations. International scientific and practical conference on "Preschool education: international experience and development prospects". November 30, 2021.
3. S. Abdumajidova. Soderjanie i znachenie ispolzovaniya steam technology and mirovom op y te razvitiya obrazovaniya . Mejdunarodnaya conference: Akademichesky nauk. September -2021. Pages 8-15
4. English Teachers: How You Can Use STEAM in Your Classroom By Jennifer Gunn <https://resilienteducator.com/classroom-resources/steam-lessons-englishclassroom>
5. Abdumajitova, S. A. (2021). STEAM TEACHING TECHNOLOGY IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AS A FACTOR OF EARLY DEVELOPMENT. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1), 10-13.